

APPRAISING THE ROLES OF SUSTAINABLE ORGANIC FARMING PRACTICES IN ENHANCING FOOD SECURITY AND LIVELIHOODS IN RURAL COMMUNITIES IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study appraised the roles sustainable organic farming practices in enhancing food security and livelihoods in rural communities in Rivers State, Nigeria. three specific objectives were used which includes to: examine the level of knowledge of farmers on sustainable organic farming practices in Rivers State, identify the sustainable organic farming practices currently practiced by farmers in the area, ascertain how organic farming methods enhance food production security and livelihoods, in the study area. Two hypotheses were stated to guide the study. A sample size of 400 crop farmers was selected through the multistage sampling technique which involved purposive, simple random and proportionate sampling techniques at various stages of the study. Questionnaire instrument designed in a 4-point Likert type rating scale was engaged to gather the data from the respondents. Weighted mean score was the descriptive statistics used to analyze the data, while linear regression was employed to test the hypotheses at 5% level of significance. The result showed that farmers' knowledge about sustainable organic farming practices ($GM = 3.28$), enhanced food production security and livelihoods in the study area. The study identified: Less use of chemicals like pesticides and herbicides by using natural ways to get rid of pests ($\bar{x} = 3.52$), the use of organic fertilisers, such as manure and compost ($\bar{x} = 3.47$), using cover crops like rye or clover to keep the soil from washing away and keep weeds down ($\bar{x} = 3.35$), using composting organic waste to make the soil more fertile and cut down on the need for synthetic fertilisers ($\bar{x} = 3.32$), promotion of biodiversity on farms, by planting a variety of crops and creating habitats for beneficial insects ($\bar{x} = 3.30$), and changes in crops, like planting legumes between cash crops to make the soil more fertile ($\bar{x} = 3.30$), among others as organic farming practices currently practiced by farmers in the area. The study recommended that: Farmers should continue to actively participate in workshops

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and training sessions to further enhance their knowledge and skills in sustainable organic farming practices; education and training of farmers on sustainable organic farming practices should be encouraged both by government and nongovernmental organizations in the state, and extension services and training programs should be provided regularly to educate farmers on the benefits of organic farming practices for their continuous implementation by the extension service providers.

Introduction

Agriculture provides the primary source of food and livelihood for billions of people, particularly in rural communities where farming is the main economic activity. As entrenched in World Bank (2022) report, approximately 80% of poor people (earning less than US\$2 in purchasing power per day) can improve their standard of livelihood, earn a decent income (purchasing power greater than US\$2), and have food security by relying on agriculture. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2020), many developing countries are engaging in agriculture as it holds an important position in improving their standard of living and contributes to community development and the growth of their national economies. Agriculture has been the most prominent driver in the reduction of extreme poverty in rural areas (World Bank, 2022). In 2015, the United Nations (UN) adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in its effort to promote sustainability in agriculture for sustainable food security worldwide.

The call for sustainability in agriculture became even more pressing as the world faces increasing environmental challenges such as climate change and the loss of biodiversity.

Sustainable crop production is essential to ensuring food security for future generations while preserving natural resources for long-term use. From the account of FAO (2020), agriculture uses 70% of the water used for human consumption and produces unacceptably high levels of pollution and waste, a situation that poses a threat to both human and environmental health, whereby a third of the food that is produced worldwide is wasted or lost. Furthermore, Altieri (2019) highlighted that the increasing demand for food is causing the heavy use of chemicals, and hybrid and transgenic crops, leading to modernizing and globalizing agriculture. Such practices can have detrimental effects on biodiversity and soil health, ultimately compromising the sustainability of agricultural systems. Furthermore, Feenstra (2016) agrees that problems such as environmental degradation, biodiversity losses, disease and pest outbreaks, soil degradation, and groundwater level depletion are all consequences of unsustainable agricultural practices. The foregoing, are some reasons it is crucial to promote sustainable agricultural practices that prioritize the health of the environment and soil, as well as the long-term viability of food production.

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The term sustainable agricultural practice has attracted the attention of policymakers, researchers and farmers alike as a means to address these pressing issues and ensure the future of food security for generations to come. Accordingly, Dunlap et al. (2013) described sustainable agriculture as the integration of a healthy environment, economic profitability, and social and economic impartiality into agricultural practices to ensure the continued success of food production while minimizing negative impacts on the environment. Also, FAO (2013) describes sustainable agriculture as the management and conservation of the natural resource base and the orientation of technological change in such a manner as to ensure the attainment of continued satisfaction of human needs for present and future generations.

From the foregoing, it can be deduced that sustainable agricultural practice can be defined as a type of farming that aims to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This involves implementing practices that are environmentally friendly, economically viable, and socially responsible. It encompasses a wide range of practices, including the use of renewable resources, the conservation of soil and water, the integration of agricultural production with the local ecosystem, and the promotion of biodiversity (Kaulotukiyacata, 2023).

In the context of farming practices in rural communities in Rivers State, sustainable agricultural practices involve utilizing organic farming methods, rotating crops, and

minimizing the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. For ages, farmers in Rivers State have relied on traditional methods that have been passed down through generations, but as the global focus on sustainability grows, there is an increasing need to adopt more modern and environmentally friendly practices to ensure long-term food security and environmental health. This shift towards sustainable agriculture can also lead to increased yields, improved soil health, and better resilience to climate change impacts. Nnaji et al. (2022) explained that modern ways of practicing organic farming include crop rotation, composting, integrated pest management, and the use of cover crops. These methods not only reduce the reliance on harmful chemicals but also promote biodiversity and overall ecosystem health. The authors explained that crop rotation, for example, helps prevent soil erosion and nutrient depletion, while composting enriches the soil with essential nutrients. Integrated pest management reduces the need for pesticides, promotes natural pest control, and reduces harm to beneficial insects. Overall, these modern organic farming practices contribute to a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system.

Food security and livelihood are two terms that can be used to describe a system that can provide consistent access to nutritious food for all individuals while also supporting the economic well-being of farmers and communities. According to Desa (2018), food security is very important for rural communities in developing countries, as it can impact sustainable livelihoods, alleviate poverty and

increase rural socio-economic growth. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined 17 ambitious goals in the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. The second goal of the SDGs focuses on ending hunger, enhancing food security, improving nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture. Even though there have been efforts from every country in trying to achieve this goal since it was adopted in 2015, the number of undernourished people have increased to 690 million in 2019 (FAO, 2020). Numerous complex and connected factors, including social, economic and environmental factors, are impeding international efforts to end hunger and achieve SDG 2. Food instability specifically implies a lack of innovative and sustainable agricultural practices in a rural community (Zhou et al., 2019).

A rural community is a term used to describe areas outside urban centers that typically have limited access to resources and infrastructure, making it difficult to implement and maintain modern agricultural techniques. These communities often rely heavily on traditional farming methods, which may not be sufficient to meet the growing demand for food sustainably. According to the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD, 2010), rural communities or rural areas, as defined in both policy-oriented and scholarly literature, are characterized by low population density, limited access to services such as healthcare and education, and a high dependence on agriculture for livelihoods. In both developing and developed countries, rural areas are defined

as the inverse or residual of urban areas (Lerner & Eakin, 2010).

Researchers are increasingly recognizing that the simple contrast between "rural" and "urban" descriptions is extremely problematic (Simon et al., 2016). Due to the wide debate about defining the terminology of a rural community, this study will define rural communities as areas outside urban centres where residents typically have limited access to services, infrastructure and economic opportunities, and depend on farming, fishing or other natural resource-based activities for their livelihoods. This definition acknowledges the complexity and diversity of rural areas around the world, highlighting the importance of considering various factors beyond population density when characterizing rural communities. Unfortunately, due to environmental issues such as climate change and natural disasters, rural communities face additional challenges in sustaining their livelihoods and accessing necessary resources; thereby increasing hunger and poverty levels in these areas.

Presently, in Nigeria, there is persistent hunger and poverty in rural communities, making food security and livelihood a critical issue. The difficulties of climate change and limited access to resources worsen these problems, emphasizing the significance of implementing contemporary organic farming techniques to increase agricultural productivity and sustainability. However, in this time of food insecurity, the role sustainable farming practices can play in enhancing food security is not clear since limited studies have directly linked the two. However, it is widely believed

that promoting organic farming practices, a form of sustainable agricultural practice can lead to increased crop yields and improved soil health, ultimately benefiting both food security and livelihoods in rural communities. Therefore, this study was aimed at assessing the roles of sustainable organic farming practices in enhancing food security and livelihoods in rural communities in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

- i. examine the level of knowledge of farmers on sustainable organic farming practices in Rivers State;
- ii. identify the sustainable organic farming practices currently practiced by farmers in the area; and
- iii. Ascertain how organic farming methods enhance food production security and livelihoods in the area.

H₀₁: The knowledge of the farmers does not significantly affect the sustainable organic practice

they adopt in the study area.

H₀₂: Organic farming methods do not significantly enhance food production security and

livelihoods in the study area

Methodology

The study was conducted in Rivers State, located in the Niger Delta region in southern Nigeria. Rivers State is the bubbling commercial hub for Nigeria's oil industry (Rivers State Government, 2019). Prior to the discovery of oil in commercial quantity in 1951, agriculture was and is still the primary occupation of the people of Rivers State till date. In a sample survey carried out by the Federal Ministry of

Agriculture and Natural Resources, about 40% of the rural inhabitants were committed to farming in 1983 and was one of the leading states in the production of yam, cassava, cocoyam, plantain and maize (Odinwa et al., 2020). Currently, production of these crops have been running down the steep slope of extinction for over twenty-five years, while their consumptions within this period are galloping uncontrollably with the attendant high cost of available crop products in the state (Odinwa et al., 2019).

The design for this study was both a descriptive survey and correlational designs. According to Nwankwo (2013), descriptive survey design enables the researcher to collect data from a large sample drawn from a given population and describing their elicited features based on the study carried out. Also, according to Nworgu (2015), a correlational design is used to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design allows researchers to determine if there is a relationship between variables and the strength of that relationship. Additionally, it provides valuable insights into the direction of the relationship, whether it is positive or negative. By adopting the descriptive survey and correlational designs, this study analyzed the extent to which sustainable organic farming practices are linked to improved food security and livelihoods in rural areas, as well as the potential connections between sustainable crop production and food security outcomes.

The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique to obtain the sample size. At the first stage, purposive sampling procedure was

employed to select twelve (12) Local Government Areas (4 each from the three senatorial districts of the state) with the aim of choosing LGAs with large farming population. In the second stage, simple random sampling method was used to select two communities from each of the twelve LGAs, giving a total of twenty-four (24) communities for the study. In the final stage, proportionate random sampling technique was adopted to select four hundred (400) farmers from the selected communities for the study. Questionnaire instrument designed in a 4-point Likert type rating scale was used to gather the data from the respondents. Weighted mean score derived from the Likert type rating scale was the descriptive statistics used to analyze the data, while linear regression was used to test the hypotheses at 5% level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Farmer's Level of knowledge about sustainable Organic farming Practices

Table 1 shows the farmers' level of knowledge about sustainable crop production in the study area. The majority of the respondents agreed to the practices, with their mean score greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. The implication of

the grand mean of 3.28 is that farmers had a substantial level of knowledge about sustainable organic farming practices in the study area. They agreed among others that the use of organic fertilizers is an important aspect of sustainable agriculture, intercropping, or planting different crops together in the same field can help improve soil health and nutrient cycling, as well as provide natural pest control and diversifying crops can help improve soil health and reduce the risk of crop failure due to pests or diseases. The farmer's knowledge of the sustainable organic farming practices in Rivers State may have stemmed from the fact that the practices are not new to them, as they appear both cultural and traditional to them. These findings are in agreement with David (2017), who observed that through decades of science and practice, the following farming practices have proven effective in achieving sustainability when used in combination: crop rotation, mixed cropping, planting cover crops and perennials, reducing or eliminating tillage, applying integrated pest management (IPM), integrating livestock and crops, adopting sustainable agroforestry practices and managing whole systems and landscapes.

Table 1: Mean rating and standard deviation of the farmers’ level of knowledge about sustainable organic farming practices in the study area

Knowledge	Responses (n = 400)			Remark
	WTS	(\bar{x})	SD	
The use of organic fertilizers is an important aspect of sustainable agriculture.	1407	3.52	0.64	High
Crop rotation is a common practice in sustainable agriculture to maintain soil fertility and reduce pest infestation	1209	3.02	0.71	High
Integrated pest management involves using a combination of biological, cultural, and mechanical practices to control pests in a sustainable way.	1340	3.35	0.81	High
Diversifying crops can help improve soil health and reduce the risk of crop failure due to pests or diseases.	1292	3.23	0.72	High
The use of chemical pesticides should be minimized in sustainable crop production to avoid negative impacts on the environment and human health.	1316	3.29	0.82	High
Use of agro forestry practices, such as planting trees alongside crops, can help improve biodiversity and provide additional sources of income for farmers?	1333	3.33	0.83	High
Conserving water resources through practices like drip irrigation and rainwater harvesting can also contribute to sustainable agriculture by reducing water waste and increasing crop yield.	1316	3.29	0.81	High
Intercropping, or planting different crops together in the same field, can help improve soil health and nutrient cycling, as well as provide natural pest control.	1392	3.48	0.67	High
Composting organic waste can help reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers and improve soil structure, while also reducing greenhouse gas emissions.	1191	2.98	0.56	High
Diversifying crops can help reduce the risk of crop failure due to disease or pests, as different crops have varying resistance levels.	1326	3.31	0.78	High
Grand Mean			3.28	

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Source: Field Survey, 2025; Criterion Mean = 2.50; WTS = Weighted Mean Score

The linear regression results on the knowledge of farmers and how it affects the sustainable organic farming practices they adopt in the study area (Table 2) showed a regression coefficient (R) of 0.61, and a t-value of 15.35 at $p = 0.00 < 0.05$, indicating a strong and a significant association between the knowledge of the farmers and sustainable practice they adopt in the study area. It showed R^2 of 0.37, indicating a 37% contribution to the sustainable

practice they adopt in the study area by the knowledge of the farmers. The implication of this result is that the knowledge of the farmers significantly enhanced the sustainable practice they adopted in the study area ($F = 235.75$ at $p < 0.05$). The findings were in tandem with Olutumise et al. (2020) who affirmed that the effects of food security and poverty on the output of cereal crop farmers hanged on the knowledge of the farmers and the contact they have with extension agents as regards organic farming.

Table 2: Linear regression results on the knowledge of farmers and how it affects the sustainable organic farming practices they adopt in the study area

Coefficient Estimates	Variables	B	S E.	t-values	P-values
Constant	Intercept	13.138 ^{xxx}	1.301	10.10	0.00
Level of Knowledge	of (X ₁)	0.609 ^{xxx}	0.040	15.35	0.00
Model Summary	Parameters	Linear Functions			
	R-value (R)	0.610			
	R Square (R ²)	0.372			
	Adjusted R Square	0.370			
	Std. Error	4.274			
	Df	398			
	F-ratio	235.754			
	P-value of F-ratio	0.000			

Source: Field Survey, 2025 xxx = 1% level of significance

Sustainable Organic Farming Practices currently used by Crop Farmers in the Study Area

The findings on the sustainable organic farming practices used by crop farmers in the study area (Table 3) showed that majority of the respondents were in conformity with the

sustainable organic farming practices, with their mean scores greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 and a grand mean of 3.32, which indicates that the sustainable organic farming practices currently being utilized by farmers in the study area include: less use of chemicals like pesticides and herbicides by using natural farming methods to get rid of pests, use of organic fertilisers, such as manure and compost, using cover crops, like rye or clover, to keep the soil from washing away and keep weeds down, and using composting organic waste to make the soil more fertile and cut down on the need

for synthetic fertilizers, among others. The findings indicate that the farmers in Rivers State are conformed to the use of sustainable organic farming practices owing to their age long practices, exposures and economic motivation and benefits they derive from those practices. The findings agree with the report of Sadati et al. (2010) that farmer’s knowledge about sustainable agriculture, job satisfaction and literacy are effective factors on farmers’ attitude toward sustainable agriculture in Khuzestan province of Iran.

Table 3: Mean rating and standard deviation of the Sustainable organic farming Practices currently being utilized by Farmers in the Study Area

Organic Farming Practices	Responses (n = 400)			Remark
	WTS	(\bar{x})	SD	
The use of organic fertilisers, such as manure and compost	1387	3.47	0.67	Agree
Changes in crops, like planting legumes between cash crops to make the soil more fertile	1319	3.30	0.82	Agree
water conservation techniques, such as collecting rainwater and using drip irrigation	1309	3.27	0.82	Agree
Regular crop rotation	1209	3.02	0.71	Agree
Integrated pest management plans, such as using pests' natural enemies to keep them in check.	1296	3.24	0.94	Agree
Forestry practices, like planting trees between crops to improve soil health and wildlife habitat	1267	3.17	0.80	Agree
Using cover crops, like rye or clover, to keep the soil from washing away and keep weeds down.	1340	3.35	0.76	Agree
Less use of chemicals like pesticides and herbicides by using natural ways to get rid of pests	1407	3.52	0.61	Agree
Promotion of biodiversity on farms: by planting a variety of crops and creating habitats for beneficial insects	1318	3.30	0.70	Agree
Using composting organic waste to make the soil	1327	3.32	0.68	Agree

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more fertile and cut down on the need for synthetic fertilisers.

Use of non-soil tillage techniques to minimize soil disturbance and maintain soil structure

1313 3.28 0.79 Agree

Grand Mean

3.32

Source: Field Survey, 2025; Criterion Mean = 2.50; WTS = Weighted Mean Score

Organic Farming Methods in enhancing Food Production Security and Livelihoods in the area of study

Results on the use of organic farming methods in enhancing Food Production Security and livelihoods (Table 4) showed that the majority of the respondents agreed on the role of organic farming methods, with their mean scores greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 and a grand mean of 3.31, an indication that organic farming methods have impact in enhancing food production security and livelihoods in the study

area, which includes: increased income opportunities for farmers, empowerment of farmers and marginalized groups in agriculture, improved health outcomes due to reduced exposure to harmful chemicals, and preservation of traditional farming knowledge and practices, among others. The findings were in harmony with Rahmann et al. (2021) report, which revealed that organic farming practices positively impact the environment, enhance the resilience of farming systems, improve small-scale farmers' income and livelihoods, promoting local food production and consumption.

Table 4: Mean rating and standard deviation of the use of organic farming methods in enhancing food production security and livelihoods in the study area

Enhancement Variables	Responses (n = 400)			
	WTS	(\bar{x})	SD	Remark
Increased soil fertility and crop yields.	1308	3.27	1.00	Agree
Reduced reliance on chemical inputs.	1306	3.27	1.01	Agree
Improved water management practices.	1304	3.26	0.98	Agree
Enhanced biodiversity and ecosystem services.	1300	3.25	1.02	Agree
Better resilience to climate change.	1302	3.25	0.85	Agree
Increased income opportunities for farmers.	1383	3.46	0.69	Agree
Improved health outcomes due to reduced exposure to harmful chemicals.	1344	3.36	0.86	Agree
Preservation of traditional farming knowledge and practices.	1327	3.32	0.68	Agree
Promotion of local food systems and markets.	1313	3.28	0.79	Agree

Empowerment of farmers and marginalized groups in agriculture. 1363 3.41 0.77 Agree

Grand Mean 3.31

Source: Field Survey, 2025; Criterion Mean = 2.50; WTS = Weighted Mean Score

Results of the linear regression on the use of organic farming methods in enhancing food production security and livelihoods (Table 5) showed a regression coefficient (R) of 0.77, indicating a strong and a significant connection between organic farming practices and food production security and livelihoods in the study area. R² of 0.59 as shown in the result indicated a 59% contribution to food production security

and livelihoods in the study area by the adoption of organic farming as a sustainable agricultural practice. The implication of this result is that the organic farming as a sustainable agricultural practice significantly enhance food production security and livelihoods in the study area (F = 576.06 at p < 0.05). The findings supported the report of Nyambi (2015), who recorded that stable farm output and increased performance significantly relates with the adoption of organic farming practices in the study area.

Table 5: Linear Regression on the use of organic farming methods in enhancing food production security and livelihoods in the study area

Coefficient Estimates	Variables	B	S E.	t-values	P-values
Constant	Intercept	14.166 ^{xxx}	0.777	18.22	0.00
Organic farming practices	(X ₁)	0.559 ^{xxx}	0.033	24.00	0.00

Model Summary	Parameters	Linear Functions
	R-value (R)	0.77
	R Square (R ²)	0.59
	Adjusted R Square	0.59
	Std. Error	3.45
	Df	398
	F-ratio	576.06
	P-value of F-ratio	0.00

Source: Field Survey, 2025

xxx = 1% level of significance

Conclusion

The result showed that farmers' knowledge about sustainable organic farming practices, enhanced food production security and

livelihoods in the study area. The study identified: Less use of chemicals like pesticides and herbicides by using natural ways to get rid of pests, using cover crops like rye or clover to

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keep the soil from washing away and keep weeds down, the use of organic fertilisers, such as manure and compost, promotion of biodiversity on farms: by planting a variety of crops and creating habitats for beneficial insects, changes in crops, like planting legumes between cash crops to make the soil more fertile, and using composting organic waste to make the soil more fertile and cut down on the need for synthetic fertilisers, among others as organic farming practices currently practiced by farmers in the area

The study concludes that the adoption of organic farming methods can enhance food production security and livelihoods in the study area.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommended the following:

1. Farmers should continue to actively participate in workshops and training sessions to further enhance their knowledge and skills in sustainable organic farming practices.
2. Education and training of farmers on sustainable organic farming practices should be encouraged both by government and nongovernmental organizations in the State.
3. Extension services and training programs should be provided regularly to educate farmers on the benefits of organic farming practices for their continuous implementation by the extension service providers.

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